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“Policy to People: Education Policy, Research Paradox and Curriculum Socialization”

Abstract

The *Forbes* magazine printed an article in 2014 “The Countries with the Most Doctoral Graduates” by Niall McCarthy which shows a comparative graph of the doctoral graduates in descending order in which India ranks fourth, the United States, Germany and the United Kingdom being the first, the second and the third. Other European countries-France, Spain, Italy-Canada, Japan and South Korea figure below India. China did not even figure. Fourth rank, defeating many European countries, Canada and Japan is perhaps a very happy news for us. But we are seriously intrigued to think of the huge and rewarding social changes and transformations in the countries that rank below us in the gradation. Higher education and research are no doubt instrumental behind these achievements whereas in India it seems they have not or least worked. The aim of this paper is to probe why research in our case is not or least committed to social empowerment and transformation like the other countries in reference. For the purpose it will examine our educational policies, existing research practice in higher education and relation between education and society in terms of curriculum to see how much space they have for the research. *I will argue that policy and research have seldom been brought down to earth in the academics of our context; therefore there has always remained a huge gap between the policy and people empowerment, the means and the end of higher education.* Ultimately, I will suggest some reformations in research practice and curriculum.

Key words: educational policy, research, curriculum, credit and grade points

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The *Forbes* magazine printed an article in 2014 “The Countries with the Most Doctoral Graduates” by Niall McCarthy which shows a comparative graph of the doctoral graduates in descending order in which India ranks fourth, the United States, Germany and the United Kingdom being the first, the second and the third. Other European countries, Canada, South Africa and Japan and South Korea graded below India (**Table 1**). China did not even figure. Fourth rank, defeating many European countries, Canada and Japan is perhaps apparently happy news for us. But we are seriously intrigued when we think of the huge and rewarding social changes and transformation higher than us in nations who rank below us. Higher education and research are no doubt instrumental behind these achievements whereas in our case this is not exactly or the least truth. We have one of the largest numbers of research graduates and, no doubt, highest number of poverty still

Countries	No. of Doctoral Graduates
United States of America	67,449
Germany	28,147
United Kingdom	25,020
India	24,300
Japan	16,039
France	13,729
South Korea	12,931
Spain	10,889
Italy	10,687
Australia	8,400
Canada	7,059
Turkey	4,516
Russia	2,223

Table 1: The countries with the most doctoral graduates (Source: www.forbes.com, accessed date 30-01-2020)

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When considered the last five year All India Survey on Higher Education (AISHE) conducted by the Ministry of Human Resource Development, the enrollment in Ph.D is ascending each year (**Table 2**) indicating that our research is gaining its magnitude.

AISHE year	Total Ph.D Awarded
2014-2015	21,830
2015-2016	24,171
2016-2017	28,779
2017-2018	34,400
2018-2019	40,813

Table 2: AISHE reports from 2014 to 2019 (Source Ministry of Human Resource Development)

The percentage of increment between 2014-2015 and 2015-2016 is 10.72 %; between 2015-2016 and 2016 -2017 is 16.01 %; 2016-2017 and 2017-2018 is 19.53 % and 2017-2018 and 2018-2019 is 18.64% (only a slight below than the previous year). This is a highly appreciative signal from the aspiring young talents desiring to explore knowledge. But given the quantity and quality scenario in reference above, this is also alarming as it might mean the continuation of the same story.

In country like ours research findings in the universities seldom become the basis of state policies. This perhaps has two reasons: 1) either the government is not interested and hence does not consider them, or 2) they are not competent and hence do not serve any purpose. A curious report appears in the *Indian Express* in May 2019 that the University Grants Commission has

decided to commission a study on the quality of PhD theses produced by Indian universities in the past ten years. The same report quotes K. Pandian, the former president of the Association of University Teachers, questioning the quality of the research: “Today, PhD has become a business and there are several people (teachers) producing PhDs by registering themselves as guides in different universities. Due to this, there is a question mark on the quality of PhDs” (Mannan 2). Pandian further observes “When PhD is made compulsory for teaching, the quality gets affected” (Mannan 3). I do not fully endorse Pandian. But the necessity that compels the move of the UGC which is supposed to be completed in the next six months involving foreign assessment agencies, really signals the same bad story of our research and higher academics.

Re-assessment of the quality of our research that we have already accredited is unfortunate in the sense that it becomes a necessity. It really pains to think on the imperative for the re-assessment paradox which forces us to consider the second reason above. It is clear our research and society are still at discord to a large extent. What causes the discord between the research and social empowerment and transformation, unlike in the other countries in reference, has become a serious concern today. Questioning the quality of our research should begin with a revisit to our educational policies. Quality should be redefined: how far our policies have made our higher education and research socially goal oriented and how far the goal is achieved should determine the first quality before anything else. This necessitates us to reflect on the National Education Policies on curriculum and research since 1968 to see how much space for research initiative they give and how serious they are.

The National Policy on Education (1968), as it is the prototype, resolves to focus on the areas like “Free and Compulsory Education”, “Status, Emoluments and Education of Teachers”, “Development of Language”, “Equalization of Educational Opportunities” etc. Nevertheless, it also considers a space for research under the head “Science Education and Research” as “...research should receive high priority” (NPE 1968, 41). Further under the head “University Education”, it states “There is need to give increased support to research in universities generally” (NPE 1968, 43). However, curriculum or directive on it does not figure anywhere. In other words, it aims at building the bases for future course of action. The National Policy on Education (1986) in Part III, “National System of Education” , Clause 3.9 gives space for research and development and commits that special measures will be taken for “network

arrangement between different institutions” (NPE 86, 5) to pool resources. It also gives space for curriculum in the Clause 3.4 as education will be based on a common core national curricular framework which will include “ the history of India’s freedom movement, the constitutional obligations and other essential to nurture national identity” (NPE 86, 4). The National Policy on Education (1986) modified in 1992, based on Acharya Ramamurti Committee report, has emphasized and kept the same curricular and research space intake.

The proposed National Policy on Education (2019) draft under the chairmanship of K. Kasturirangan has emphasized on the serious need of an autonomous institution, National Research Foundation, to be set up through an act of parliament and has recommended the revision of the Choice Based Credit System (CBCS) curriculum for more flexibility. A clear picture of the space on the emphasis on curriculum and research thus emerges. Accordingly, research initiatives have been taken through several agencies in which ICSSR is playing a vital role providing domains, guidelines and fund. UGC scholarship like JRF, Indian Council of Historical Research (ICHR) JRF for all competent research scholars and Maulana Azad National Fellowship (MANF) for minority students in research are other examples. All the initiatives deserve appreciation and gratification; policy has willingly invested enough both time and fund. But this does not solve the problem. How does the research become still incompetent then? Why the goal “all round development, material and spiritual” (NPE 68, 86, 92) still seem only partly or not realized as in other countries? These are complex questions to introspect further.

Having policy for research and also initiatives through different agencies being one of the bases, competence on the part of the researchers becomes another suspected area. However, there are already regulations to ensure it. Ph.D entrance tests conducted at universities and proposals regulated by the various research boards and NET as the base for JRF allocation are a few examples. In other words, the competence on the part of the researchers is well ensured before the beginning. Until this point, the research seems to have no serious issues which might deviate and derail it. However, once started under a guide, in the process, it might encounter two probable barrages in general: 1) theory/perspective to be employed and 2) the field of engagement or area. As for the first, I will take the example of the general practice in humanities, literature. A scholar is generally asked to adopt a prevalent theory/perspective, or combination of perspectives, as the tool of inspection. Marxist criticism and Post-structuralism besides many

other twentieth century perspectives, for instance, are in general vogue. The scholar does not, or is rather not allowed, to test the validity of the theory for the native context and content and hence the research begins in the light of a perspective incepted, framed and practiced long back in an entirely different-socially, historically, culturally, civilizationally- foreign context.

Marxist theory, though it has variables, has a very distinct origin in the *Das Capital*. First of all this is a research on European civilization starting with early Greece. In Greece, Marx sees the society divided into masters and slaves, in Medieval Europe into landlords and serfs and in the modern Bourgeoisie and Proletariat. Social division is the basis of power for them. Therefore, he recommends a revolution that only can change the power dynamic. When taken to research, the theory assumes four basics: 1) literature is a “superstructure”, a social formation, a cause and consequence of revolutionary changes that have come through tussle in power relation, 2) the work of a literature is to become/give a space for the cause and consequence of the changes in its fabric, 3) the work of a writer/author is to code the cause and consequence of the changes, and 4) the work of a critic/research scholar is to decode the experience of the literature and the writer to explore the formation and de-formation of the power dynamic. Our scholar in the very beginning thus gets hijacked in the sense that he has to accept his work area is already a split, fringed and dislocated site between powerful/exploiting and powerless/exploited figures which might not be necessarily true in his/her context.

The Post-structuralism which has its germs in Jacques Derrida, a Professor at the Yale University in America, begins as a linguist and gradually carries his idea to philosophy and language of human sciences, particularly anthropology. His idea of “differance” and “deconstruction” penetrated all the post-structuralist theories like Post-colonialism, New-historicism, Readers’ Response Theory and Subaltern Studies. Derrida denies the origin and existence of permanence in meaning of words at first. He says, “The center is not the center” (Derrida, 01) meaning we can never have a central origin. Gradually the idea is extended, rather carried up to every other knowledge discourse and literature study is not an exception. The denial of the origin/centre is often interpreted as an enabling phenomenon and therefore research often takes deconstructive model under this tool. This is a paradox and the paradox is that the paradox lies within the idea. To deny the center, paradoxically Derrida has to create a centre at first, “The

center is not the centre”; a sentence is already a centre because it will certainly have a central syntactical meaning. In other words, a scholar in terms of a research directed by the idea of “deconstruction” has to start with a paradox; course with the paradox and through them will end in a paradox. The problem with Marx and Derrida, therefore, when taken to research is that 1) the first divides and the second denies! and 2) gets direction and conviction from a culturally and historically different foreign model which does more justice to itself.

Whereas, Marx is valid in European context and he might do justice there. He observes the European society at the height of the industrial revolution that was creating and maintaining the new models for the medieval feudalist class structure which was the take-way of early Greece/Roman structure where slavery was the means of economy. Rousseau has noted Aristotle saying “that men are by no means equal naturally, but that some are born for slavery and others for dominion” (Rousseau 27). This became a legacy and in European context it was abolished completely only in 1834. Derrida shares the post-war European psychology which is marked by a sense of absurdity which owes much of its origin in the war catastrophe, the sense of nothingness. Precisely, his observation that nothing is central and permanent then is a great consolation for them. Indian society in both the sense is different: slavery was never our means of economy; neither have we been devastated by the deadly wars like the first and the second world wars. Therefore, the perspectives in our context look more like a lawyer looking for problems in innocent families to do justice to his/her own job.

Research thus has chances for deviation, for being directionless under the practice in vogue. Why do the higher academics practice essentialism of the unfiltered, not validated perspectives? This might incite different inferences. One of them is the issue of research ethics, which implies, that I consider, is the identification of research problem/area in the society. I am of the opinion that at the academic level, social problem that can become the research problem seldom gets prominence. What I would like to suggest is that in the recent academics both the scholars and authorities are never thoroughly engaged with the societies, social issues that need solution through research. Our classes are conducted within the four walls of a room; societies are taught through texts and in some cases video clips. Even in the revised curriculum under the CBCS system, though it allows pools of courses pertaining to have co-relation with the social

needs from where students have liberty to have their choices, the direct social engagement does not figure. Whereas there are practices of social engagement in certain subjects like Social Work but they are more an engagement than learning from the society, that is to say the society is not their text; it is approached through already defined course-modules. Thus in our practices, the institution and the societies stand distant apart; texts and clips considered for studies suffer several editions; the live and original social text is always missing. Therefore, academic engagement with live society is always duplicate. And accordingly, the live/real issues/problems of the societies that need further enquiry for solutions are not identified. Our academics do not train, rather do not have a system, and prepare future scholars in them who can orient their research to the social issues/problems they have identified. In such case a research is not focused. This research and curriculum issues are not unique of India, they are also equally true of Nepal.

Therefore, two things are suggestive here, one for the curriculum and another for the research. The challenge is if the live society cannot come literally into the academics which otherwise is a must, then it is the high time the academics should literally go to the society. And this is possible in terms of curriculum, that is to say, the live society should become our texts and clips. A complete paradigm shift, that is taking all the classes to society, is perhaps not possible. But we can at least think of a course-model of certain credits that students learn from the live society. This is what this paper likes to call “curriculum socialization”. This will have four components: 1) academic-course planning, credits, engagement time, logistics etc. 2) Society-text, that is selection of the society as live learning area, 3) partnership, that is a course like this will further get strengthen if conducted in partnership with other social institutions, NGOs , social organizations having shared interest it is where a partnership between India and Nepal be forged as we have many shared social issues-human trafficking, poverty, drug abuse, culture, heritage, history ,literature etc, and 4) Assessment- that is the question of assessing the credit points. It is highly suggestive that the traditional teacher centric assessment model should collapse. The target society, the partners should grade the students through established systems like feedback forms. The study institution can grade through the system of presentation of ideas by the students, panel discussion, peer grading system etc. The students may also post their learning in the social media and the number of views/likes may be considered for assessment.

As the perspective for research there is an imperative to think for a native problem-native critical tool/perspective for solution. Bill Ashcroft, Gareth Griffiths, and Helen Tiffin have categorized context specific indigenous critical models and their modus operandi in their seminal book *The Empire Writes Back* (1989). In the fourth chapter ‘Theory at the Crossroads: Indigenous theory and post-colonial reading’ the writers explore the working models of indigenous theory in the context of India, Africa, Caribbean and the settler colonies whose critical implementation would mean decolonization of the Eurocentric perspectives. The native traditions have “diglossic oral cultures” in which bilingualism has been strongly established. So the writers have a conviction that they have a huge potentiality of critical concepts from which a modern native critical theory can be designed. In the Indian context, they trace a native critical tradition in Sanskrit from 200 B.C. to 1780 A.D and other vernacular literatures like Tamil and Urdu. Thus they write,

The earliest extant work of Indian criticism in Sanskrit, the *Natya Shastra of Bharata*, dates from c. 200 B.C. and there followed an unbroken tradition of commentary for some two thousand years to the work of Jagannatha (c. AD 1780). Literatures in other languages, such as Tamil and Urdu, also have extensive and ancient critical traditions (Ashcroft 116).

They also consider the attempt of the Indian critic like K. Krishnamoorthy¹ to see the possibility of use of Indian classical concept of “rasa,” “dhvani” and “alankara” (suggestion, emotion and rhetoric) against the imported concepts whose concern is to give a sense of Indianess to mode of expression, as a model of critical enquiry. They have also noted similar native theories in operation in Africa in terms of “negritude”, settler colonies (USA, Australia and Canada) “New Criticism” and in the Carribean Island “Creolization”. The idea is to replace foreign models and bring research into the tract.

What can at least be inferred is that our research and social goals are still distant apart. Our scholars are not fully made aware of/trained in the social issues through academics. But the scholar if trained in the social issues/problems through the curriculum socialization and using native tools of enquiry, our research will be certainly back in track; both the means and the end will get mutually empowered. The remaining bases like will and fund, we already have. Only

then our policy, research and curriculum can become complementary to each other; only then our policy will literally reach our people.

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